

Burnout and other psychosocial factors in Portuguese judges: The influence of sociodemographic and work variables

Matilde Maia Pratas, João Paulo Dias, Gustavo Ferreira da Veiga, Luciana Sotero

¹ Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, University of Coimbra (FPCEUC), Portugal, matilde.m.pratas@gmail.com | ORCID: 0009-0000-0856-5338; ² Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra (CES-UC), Portugal, jpdias@ces.uc.pt | ORCID: 0000-0003-0884-8746; ³ CES-UC, gustavoveiga@ces.uc.pt | ORCID: 0000-0002-2161-9297; ⁴ CES-UC and FPCEUC, lucianasotero@fpce.uc.pt | ORCID: 0000-0001-8393-2775

Abstract: Recent studies show that the experience of stress in the judiciary is a phenomenon with an impact on the health of the judicial professionals, but also on the level of performance and ability to fulfill their duties. This study aims to evaluate the burnout inducing symptoms and other psychosocial factors of Portuguese judges working, in Judicial Courts of First Instance, attending to sociodemographic (age and gender) and work characteristics (years as judge, displacement and satisfaction with the place of assignment). A sample of 413 Portuguese judges completed an online survey with (i) a sociodemographic and working data questionnaire, (ii) the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ) to evaluate health indicators (general health, sleeping problems and stress) and (iii) the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) to evaluate burnout. Regarding the working characteristics, the results showed that the satisfaction with the place of assignment were correlated with the general health, sleeping problems and stress, and also it was a good predictor of judges' burnout. Furthermore, more years of service was also associated with worse health indicators and burnout. The relevance of the satisfaction of the place of assignment demonstrated the need to reevaluate the norms in which public tenders are carried out, with the aim of creating a fairer appointment system that causes less damage to the life of judges.

Keywords: health, burnout, working characteristics, Portuguese judges.

Burnout e outros fatores psicossociais na magistratura judicial portuguesa: A influência de variáveis sociodemográficas e de trabalho

Resumo: Estudos recentes mostram que o stresse na magistratura judicial é um fenómeno com impacto na saúde dos profissionais judiciais, mas também a nível do desempenho e capacidade de cumprimento das suas funções. Este estudo tem como objetivo avaliar os sintomas cujo impacto potencia estados de *burnout* e outros fatores psicossociais dos/as juizes/as portugueses/as que trabalham nos Tribunais Judiciais de Primeira Instância atendendo às características sociodemográficas (idade e género) e de trabalho (anos de serviço, deslocação e satisfação com o local de colocação). Uma amostra de 413 juizes/as respondeu a um inquérito online com (i) um questionário de dados sociodemográficos e de trabalho, (ii) o Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ) para avaliar indicadores de saúde (saúde geral, problemas em dormir e stresse) e (iii) o Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) para avaliar o *burnout*. Em relação às características do trabalho, os resultados mostraram que a satisfação com o local de colocação esteve correlacionada com a saúde geral, problemas em dormir e stresse e também foi um bom preditor de *burnout* dos/as juizes/as. Além disso, mais anos de serviço também foram associados a piores indicadores de saúde e *burnout*. A relevância da satisfação com o local de colocação demonstrou a necessidade de reavaliar as normas em que se realizam os concursos públicos, com o objetivo de criar um sistema de nomeação mais justo e que cause menos dano à vida dos/as juizes/as.

Palavras-chave: saúde, *burnout*, características do trabalho, juizes/as portugueses/as.

1. Introduction

Working conditions have an impact on workers' health and well-being. In recent decades there have been improvements in working conditions, but new risks have also emerged, such as physical and emotional exhaustion and interpersonal conflicts, associated with work contexts that require increased productivity, and therefore generate more competitive professional environments, which are, consequently, more harmful to the health and wellbeing of workers (Sauter et al., 2002, Santana et al., 2020). Psychosocial risk factors associated with the profession, in conjunction with sociodemographic variables such as age and gender, and with characteristics inherent to the type of work, can lead to the development of stress and burnout, with nefarious consequences for the exercise of the profession (Marchand et al., 2005; Ribeiro et al., 2018; Rosário et al., 2017). Assessing work circumstances in courts as regards the judicial professions is a relevant object of study, since the functioning of these entities can jeopardise the quality of the justice that is provided to citizens. Concerning the application of justice, judges hold total decision-making powers, and it is therefore essential to assess the conditions in which they work as well as analyse the impact of these conditions on their health. The literature on this topic is scarce in respect to the Portuguese judiciary, lacking empirical evidence on the effects of work and its characteristics on this professional class. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the health and burnout of Portuguese judges working in Judicial Courts of First Instance according to sociodemographic characteristics (age and gender) and work characteristics (years as judge, displacement and satisfaction with the place of assignment). This cross-sectional study follows on from a previous research project on the working conditions of the judicial professions (judges, public prosecutors, and bailiffs) which concluded that there is an increasing risk of burnout among these professionals (Dias et al., 2024). This study aims to contribute to the improvement of the conditions inherent in the exercise of the judicial professions.

2. The work context in courts

Although the professional status of judges is strongly associated with an attitude of general respect from the vast majority of society, the nature of their work, the workload required, the responsibility and decision-making associated with meeting deadlines cause these professionals to be particularly vulnerable to stress and to deterioration of their physical and mental health. According to Ciocoiu et al. (2010), there is at present empirical evidence to prove that "(...) judges belong to a profession that is among the most exposed and vulnerable to occupational stress, with manifestations at various levels, including health and work ability" (p. 134). This being the case, it is fundamental to study the causes, risks and stressors underlying the profession of judge (Tsai & Chan, 2010).

The extent of studies aimed at understanding working conditions and their impact on judges is still rather small when compared to sectors of activity such as health professionals (Copanitsanou, 2017; Eisch et al., 2022) or education (Richards et al., 2018), for example. The demands imposed by the responsibilities inherent to the role of judge can be a catalyst for negative impacts on well-being and health (Chamberlain & Miller, 2009). In parallel with a formal evaluation of the performance, the objectives and the parameters achieved by judges, it is also important to understand that their professional component is inseparable from a personal nature and a set of individual characteristics that structurally incorporate the performance of their duties. They are more than just professionals with a

high status, with demands and responsibilities, they are also subjects with particular needs (Blackham, 2019; Ng, 2014).

According to the literature, there are specific stress factors in the work of judges, such as: the complexity of cases under trial, decision-making processes, and the disruption of judges' daily schedule arising from the unpredictability associated with the exercise of their duties (Miller & Flores, 2007). Additionally, being exposed to reports of violent crimes, participating in high profile media cases or even the nature and jurisdiction of the court where judges sit are all work characteristics that may cause particularly high levels of stress (Flores et al., 2009).

It is therefore necessary to investigate the conditions that would allow a balance between individual and family needs and the demands and responsibilities imposed by the exercise of a judicial profession, so that these professionals can fulfil their duties and meet the responsibilities that are laid on them (Roach Anleu & Mack, 2014; Na et al., 2017).

3. Burnout and other psychosocial factors in work contexts

The relentless pursuit of modernisation and constant updating in the labour market has brought significant changes, both at a social and labour level, prompting the need to change the guidelines and rules that guide workers' lives. The workforce is not seen merely as workforce, but as a group of human beings deserving of working conditions and stability in the workplace.

The drastic and rapid changes that have occurred have given rise to certain fears, with concerns about the reduction in job security and the increase in demands and workload. Working conditions have begun to be seen as potential risk factors for workers' well-being, with some concerns raised in terms of physical and mental health.

It is in this context that worries arise about psychosocial factors at work and how they can be associated with a negative impact on the health and well-being of workers. These psychosocial factors are related to working conditions and are represented through the organization and management of work, which translate into work demands, the availability of support from organizations, rewards and interpersonal relationships in the workplace (Jain et al., 2021, pp. 1-2).

The International Labour Organization (1986, p. 3) defines psychosocial risk factors as "interactions between the work environment, work content, organizational conditions and workers' capabilities, needs, culture and personal considerations outside of work that may, through perception and experience, influence health, work performance and job satisfaction". According to Portuguese Directorate General of Health (DGS, 2021, p. 26), psychosocial risk factors can be divided into the following categories: a) nature, content and workload; b) organizational conditions and working time and socio-relational contexts of work; and c) work/life relationship. The consecration of these factors as risks depends on the meaning and value attributed to them individually by workers, trying to understand whether they cause imbalances between demands and resources and whether they are not controllable.

Professions with very high levels of demand are those in which workers suffer the most from health problems, such as mental health problems and burnout, as well as heart diseases and musculoskeletal disorders (Jain et al., 2021). These health problems generate consequences that have an impact both at an individual level, on the part of the worker, and at an organizational level, leading to an increase in absenteeism, with

negative effects on productivity, effective resource management and employers' savings (Rosário et al., 2017).

This has brought attention to the potential impact of stressors in the workplace. Stressors are factors that generate a psychological state of discomfort which, according to Na et al. (2017), affects workers' attitudes and behaviour, including their physical, psychological and emotional well-being. When exposure to these factors is prolonged over time, problems with performance and the level of commitment to work tasks may emerge, potentially leading to such phenomena as burnout and professional dissatisfaction (Hassell et al., 2010). Although different, both stress and burnout can be associated with factors intrinsic to the nature of the profession itself and affect the quality of life of workers (Gomes, 2022). While stress corresponds to a moment of adaptation with physical and mental symptoms, burnout is a breakdown in this ability to adapt which in turn causes chronic functioning difficulties (Queirós, 2005).

On the first years of research, the concept of occupational stress corresponded to an emotional state of discomfort resulting from factors present at work and characterised by such symptoms as tension, dissatisfaction, and feelings of frustration and low efficiency, which can lead to emotional exhaustion (Martins et al., 1996, cited in Malagris & Fiorito, 2006). Later, in 2014, the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA) clarified that occupational stress is felt "when the demands placed on the work environment exceed the ability of workers to withstand (or control) them" (p.14). Stress in the workplace translates into an increase in sick leave and absenteeism, decreased productivity, frequent delays, and even an exacerbated use of drugs (Sadir et al., 2010). Experiencing authoritarianism from the leadership, distrust, pressure, working hours, monotony, personal dissatisfaction and excessively long working hours are recurring stressors in the world of work (Malagris & Fiorito, 2006). When professional demands outstrip rewards, there can be a high level of strain and numerous diseases can occur, with burnout being one of the most prevalent (Bakker et al., 2000; Malagris & Fiorito, 2006; Mota et al., 2020).

The International Classification of Diseases tells us that burnout is a consequence of chronic work stress not having been successfully managed. It is not a medical condition, but rather an occupational, context-specific phenomenon (WHO, 2022). Burnout syndrome was initially considered a psychological condition associated with professionals whose area of work requires recurrent contact with other people, such as in professions pertaining to Social Work, Nursing, Medicine or Psychology. However, over the years, studies have demonstrated that burnout can occur in any professional area, since the risk factors that produce this syndrome are present in a wide variety of work contexts (Demerouti et al., 2001).

According to Lian et al. (2021), burnout can be defined as "a prolonged response to chronic emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job" (p. 2). According to ICD-11 (WHO, 2022), the following dimensions are often associated with burnout: i) feelings of exhaustion or energy depletion; ii) increased mental distance from one's job or feelings of negativity or cynicism towards work; and iii) a sense of ineffectiveness and lack of personal/professional fulfilment. Delbrouck (2006) describes the three dimensions of burnout as: i) emotional exhaustion; ii) depersonalisation; and iii) a feeling of incompetence.

As regards the causes of burnout, Delbrouck (2006) distinguishes between internal and external factors. External factors are associated with such aspects as workload, lack

of sleep, excessive responsibilities, confrontation with impotence and death, increased expectations and lack of support in the workplace. As for the internal factors, the author considers that there are psychological traits that play a major role in how burnout develops, emphasising the following characteristics: anxiety, a spirit of enterprise, a desire to please, an overly severe sense of self-criticism, wanting to do everything by yourself and a “saviour” mentality.

In short, increased demands, the degradation of the social environment in the workplace and a more intense workload, among other factors, can lead to the emergence of occupational stress and burnout and consequently, to a decrease in productivity and quality of work in the workplace (Pereira et al., 2022; Rosário et al., 2017).

4. Assessing psychosocial factors and burnout in the workplace

Working conditions are a relevant dimension that should be evaluated in studies on the impact of the work context on workers’ health. Most recent studies have sought to understand the interaction between the workplace and workers’ health, namely in situations involving accidents at work, occupational diseases, heart disease or exposure to hazardous chemicals (Gupta & Kristensen, 2008). The psychosocial factors at work cannot be considered, per se, as a negative aspect inherent to the profession. However, their impact can be reduced if there is active involvement by the management bodies and teams of organizations in preventing the risks associated with these factors (Jain et al., 2021).

According to the literature, workers experience the most health problems in those professions with the highest levels of demand. These demands can be divided into three domains that should be monitored because of their high potential for causing episodes of stress and burnout: physical demands, such as exacerbated physical exertion; psychological demands, such as interpersonal conflicts or pressure from one’s superiors; and contractual demands, namely job security, from the point of view of compliance with contractual requirements (Marchand et al., 2005; Schaufeli, 2017). It was also found that health problems generate personal and organisational consequences, leading to increased absenteeism, with negative effects on productivity, on effective resource management and on the economy of employers (Collins et al., 2005; Rosário et al., 2017).

Assessing psychosocial factors in the work environment is particularly complex in the absence of a general consensus on how to define and evaluate work-related psychosocial factors. Among the various tools available, the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ; Kristensen et al., 2005) deserves special mention. It was created to enable a multidimensional and integrated assessment of all the aspects that evoke the concept of work-related psychosocial factors (Kristensen et al., 2005). Thus, it is a valid, easy to understand instrument for assessing psychosocial factors in the workplace that explain stress as a consequence of high demand at work and low social support (Kristensen et al., 2005). Following the example of several countries that use the COPSOQ, Portugal has also used it with the aim of assessing the impact of psychosocial factors at work and contributing to scientific progress in the field of occupational health, in order to assess the effect of psychosocial factors at work. These psychosocial factors refer to the “characteristics inherent to the conditions and organization of work that affect the health of individuals, through psychological and physiological processes” (Silva, 2012, p. 6). Psychosocial risks are the result of the combination of the individual, their living conditions and their working conditions (Silva, 2012).

Initially, burnout was considered a psychological condition associated with professionals whose work area required recurring contact with other people, such as in the professions of Social Work, Nursing, Medicine or Psychology. However, over the years, studies have shown that burnout can arise in any professional area, since the risk factors that give rise to this disease are present in the most varied work contexts (Demerouti et al., 2001).

5. Materials and Methods

Within the scope of a broader research project¹, a protocol was then created with a comprehensive questionnaire, covering different thematic blocks. The instrument considered questions related with sociodemographic and socio-professional characteristics of participants, questions about working conditions based on the European Working Conditions Survey (Eurofound; 2016), questions from the Portuguese medium version of the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire II (COPSOQ) (Silva et al., 2012) and questions of the Portuguese and Brazilian version of the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) (Sinval et al., 2019).

In this article, only the results of some indicators obtained from this instrument will be presented. Due to the magnitude of data, it is not possible to integrate everything in a single article, therefore, the authors decided to segment the presentation and discussion of results into different articles. In this case, will be analysed psychosocial factors related with health, professional exhaustion and satisfaction with regards to some of the specific characteristics of the work of judges.

5.1. Participants and Procedures

The Ethics Committee of the Centre for Social Studies (CES) of the University of Coimbra approved the study and the research protocol, and an authorisation to use the relevant instruments was obtained from their respective authors. Completion of the research protocol was preceded by informed consent, which included information about the research project, the team responsible for the project, information about the rules for participation and the mandatory confidentiality of the data collected (All European Academies, 2018).

The research protocol was thoroughly reviewed and corrected and later, in the pilot study phase, it was administered to two members of the judiciary. This was followed by a moment of dialogue between the team and the respondents, with a spoken reflection on the items. Their opinion was key to ensure the adequacy, correction and clarification of the protocol's content. This review provided a deeper understanding of the specificities of the

¹ This cross-sectional study follows on from a previous project, namely "QUALIS – Quality of Justice in Portugal" (PTDC/DIR OUT/29039/2017) which assessed the working conditions of judicial professions, such as Judges, Public Prosecutors and Clerks. After analysing the results obtained, it was possible to realize that it would be relevant to investigate issues such as professional burnout and stress in the judicial system. Thus, a new research project emerged, entitled "Study on working conditions, professional exhaustion, health and well-being of Portuguese judges", which had the general objective of evaluating working conditions, exhaustion professional (burnout) and the well-being of judges working in the common jurisdiction and administrative and tax courts, in the various instances in Portugal. This project, which began in 2022 and ended in December 2023, was developed by a team from the Permanent Observatory for Justice of the Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra (OPJ/CES), which focused on areas such as Psychology, Law and Sociology, for a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach to the topic. Ultimately, the focus was to enable the acquisition of knowledge, that allows for greater understanding regarding the health and well-being of the judicial professions and the proposal of recommendations, to change the current status quo of occupational health in courts.

questions so that they could be interpreted in accordance with the requirements established by the research team when setting the project objectives.

Data collection took place between December 5, 2022 and January 31, 2023, being authorised by the High Council of Judges and the High Council of Administrative and Tax Courts. The online research protocol, built on the LimeSurvey platform, was disseminated electronically with the support of the abovementioned High Councils and the Association of Portuguese Judges. This study considered only the responses of first instance courts judges, excluding those sitting in higher judicial courts and administrative and tax courts.

5.2. Instrument and Measures

From the comprehensive questionnaire developed, in this article was used data from some blocks. The component related to Sociodemographic and Complementary Data Questionnaire was developed specifically for this study, allowing the collection of sociodemographic data (e.g., gender and age) and socio-professional data (e.g., years as judge and displacement). An item was included to assess satisfaction with the place of assignment, using a Likert scale with 5 response levels from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).

From the COPSOQ, was used the health indicators segment, that considered elements related to general health, sleeping problems and stress. The General Health dimension is assessed through one item (i.e. "In general, you feel that your health is...") from 5 levels of response (from excellent to deficient). For the present study, scoring was inverted, with higher scores corresponding to a better perception of one's health.

The Sleep Problems dimension is evaluated through two items (i.e., "Did you have difficulty falling asleep?", "Did you wake up several times during the night and then found it difficult to get back to sleep?" answered on a Likert scale from 1 (Never/Hardly ever) to 5 (Always). The Stress dimension is assessed through two items ("Do you feel irritable?", "Do you feel anxious?"), rated on a Likert scale from 1 (Never/Hardly ever) to 5 (Always). The Portuguese version of COPSOQ has the following internal consistency values: Cronbach's α of .84 for Sleep Problems and Cronbach's α of .73 for Stress (Silva, 2012). The internal consistency values found in the present study were: Cronbach's α of .82 for Sleep Problems and Cronbach's α of .77 for Stress.

To evaluate the professional exhaustion inducing symptoms, the Portuguese version of OLB was used (Demerouti & Nachreiner, 1998; Sinval et al., 2019). This tool considers 16-items that assesses burnout in two dimensions: 1) Emotional Exhaustion; and 2) Disengagement. In addition to calculating a global score that translates the level of burnout, it is also possible to calculate an individual score for each of the dimensions. In this inventory, the items are scored on a Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The validation study of the Portuguese version of the OLB revealed good consistency indicators, namely: Disengagement ($\alpha = .91$), Emotional Exhaustion ($\alpha = .87$) and global burnout score ($\alpha = .93$) (Sinval et al., 2019). In the present study, the inventory showed good internal consistency values: Disengagement ($\alpha = .87$), Emotional Exhaustion ($\alpha = .86$) and global burnout score ($\alpha = .90$) (Kline, 2011).

5.3. Statistical Analyses

The statistical analyses were preceded by inspection of missing values. Missing data analysis followed to examine whether values were missing completely at random (MCAR) with Little's MCAR test (Little, 1988). The test was not significant, suggesting that values

were missing entirely at chance. Normality assumptions were checked in all the instruments by analysing the values of kurtosis and symmetry. Such assumptions were met in OLBI scores. The COPSOQ dimensions however do not follow a normal distribution. The internal consistency of the subscales used in this study was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Descriptive analyses aimed at characterising the sample were performed. The relationship between sociodemographic variables (age and gender) and work variables (years as judge, displacement from home, satisfaction with the place of assignment) with health indicators (general health, sleep problems, stress) and burnout (disengagement, exhaustion and burnout) was analysed. A Mann-Whitney U test was performed to evaluate whether the variables assessed differed by gender. Spearman's rank correlation was used to assess the relationship between age and years as judge and the health and burnout variables. A Mann-Whitney U test was also performed to evaluate whether the variables assessed differed considering whether judges were displaced or not. The relationship between satisfaction with the place of assignment and health and burnout variables was assessed by a Spearman's rank correlation. Lastly, based on the results obtained, a linear regression model was tested. Data collection processing and statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 28.

6. Results

6.1 Sociodemographic characterisation and psychosocial indicators

The sample consisted of 413 judges (i.e., judges working in judicial courts of first instance), corresponding to 31.5% of the sample (N = 1311, as of January 31, 2023). The majority of respondents are female (70.3%), aged between 41 and 50 (M = 47.4; SD = 7.06) and have a university degree (75.2%). As concerns years as judge, the category most represented is between 16 and 25 years of age (48.2%), table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characterisation of the sample

	Categories	Sample	
		<i>n</i>	%
Gender	Female	289	70.0
	Male	122	29.5
Age	<30	4	1.0
	31-40	59	14.3
	41-50	200	48.4
	51-60	139	33.7
	>61	11	2.7
Education Level	Degree	310	75.1
	Master's Degree	100	24.2
	PhD	3	0.7
Years as judge	<5	49	11.9
	6-15	117	28.3
	16-25	200	48.4
	26-35	45	10.9
	>36	2	0.5
Total		413	

With the aim of obtaining a comprehensive perspective on the results obtained in the judiciary in comparison with the Portuguese population, the validation results of COPSOQ (Silva et al., 2012) and OLBI (Sinval et al., 2019) for the Portuguese population were analyzed (Table 2). Accordingly, the values obtained show that the participants obtained poorer results in the health indicators in all dimensions (poorer general health, more sleep problems and higher stress), showing that Portuguese judges are one of the professional areas whose health indicators show the worst results. Participants presented higher scores in all burnout indicators, which translates into worse disengagement indicators and particularly, exhaustion indicators. These results will be further explored later in this article, in the section reserved for discussion.

Table 2. Comparisons with the Portuguese Population

Instrument	Scores	Judges Results		Portuguese population (Silva et al., 2012)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
COPSOQ Indicators	General Health	3.3	1.02	3.44	.91
	Sleep Problems	3.91	.99	2.46	1.05
	Stress	3.32	.87	2.70	.90
Instrument	Scores	Judges Results		Portuguese population (Sinval et al., 2019)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
OLBI Indicators	Disengagement	2.82	.77	2.56	.87
	Emotional Exhaustion	3.40	.67	2.80	.75
	Burnout (Global score)	3.13	.64	2.69	.73

6.2. The influence of sociodemographic and work characteristics on health and burnout

The results from the Mann-Whitney U test indicated that there were no significant differences in General Health, Sleep Problems and Stress by gender. The Spearman's rank correlation performed to assess the relationship between age and General Health, Sleep Problems and Stress revealed that there was a negative correlation between the age and General Health ($r(413) = -.211, p < .001$). No correlation was found between age and the other variables. Years as judge was also negatively correlated with General Health ($r(413) = -.128, p = .009$). No other correlations were found between years as judge and the remaining variables. The Mann-Whitney U test results indicated that judges who were displaced had significantly higher sleep problems than non-displaced judges ($U = 13687, z = 1.89, p = .06$). Being displaced had no significant difference on the remaining variables. Satisfaction with the place of assignment was positively correlated with General Health ($r(402) = .185, p < .001$), and negatively with Sleep Problems ($r(402) = -.181, p < .001$) and Stress ($r(402) = -.170, p < .001$).

A Mann-Whitney U Test revealed that men had significantly higher scores on the OLBI Disengagement subscale than women ($U = 15271, z = -2.15, p = .032$). There was no significant difference between the OLBI Exhaustion subscale and OLBI total score by

gender. The Spearman's rank correlation performed to assess the relationship between age and OLBI scores revealed that there was a positive correlation between age and Disengagement subscale ($r(413) = .183, p < .001$), a positive correlation with Burnout scores ($r(413) = .152, p = .002$) and no correlation with the Exhaustion subscale. Similarly, the Spearman's rank correlation revealed that there was a positive correlation between years as judge and Disengagement subscale ($r(413) = .223, p < .001$), a positive correlation with Burnout scores ($r(413) = .169, p < .001$) and no correlation with the Exhaustion subscale. The Mann-Whitney U test results showed no significant differences between judges who were displaced and judges not displaced in Burnout Scores and subscales. Satisfaction with the place of assignment was negatively correlated with Disengagement subscale ($r(413) = -.237, p < .001$), Exhaustion subscale ($r(413) = -.237, p < .001$) and Burnout scores ($r(413) = -.247, p < .001$).

6.3. Burnout predictors

Considering the results obtained, we decided to test the suitability of a linear regression model to the overall OLBI score. Before conducting the linear regression, we found that the independent variables age and years as judge had high collinearity values, since their correlation shows a value of $r = .840$, against a desirable value of less than .7 (Tabachnik & Fidell, 2018). Thus, it was decided that age should be removed from this model to exclude the interference of these values. A significant regression was found ($F[2],[399] = [23,061](4), p = < .001$). The R^2 was .104, indicating that years as judge and satisfaction with place of placement explained approximately 10.4% of the variance in Burnout scores.

7. Discussion

Organisational principles and working conditions play a major role in workers' health, and the study of working conditions and their impact is an increasingly pertinent object of research (EU-OHSA, 2012). Judges, as key actors in the judicial system, are subject to social and political pressure, evaluation and criticism with respect to their performance (Brody, 2008; Guimarães et al., 2020). In the context of justice, there are some studies on health and well-being in the legal professions and the judiciary (Sharma et al., 2010; Tsai et al., 2009). However, research on this sector of activity is still scarce. Hence, the aim of this study was to assess health and burnout indicators in Portuguese judges sitting in judicial courts of first instance, according to sociodemographic characteristics (age and gender) and work characteristics (years as judge, displacement and satisfaction with the place of assignment), with a view to contributing to the improvement of the conditions in which judicial professions are exercised.

First, the findings of this study showed that judges had worse health indicators when compared to the rest of the Portuguese population (Table 2). On average, judges had a less favourable perception of their overall health, sleep quality and the stress experienced. Also, with regard to burnout judges presented higher average scores, compared to the reference values obtained for the Portuguese population. In particular, the results showed that, although judges had higher average values in both dimensions of the burnout scale, this difference is most noticeable in the Exhaustion dimension. These results corroborate studies that show the particular vulnerability of the profession of judge to occupational stress, with manifestations in terms of their health (Ciocoiu et al., 2010).

With regard to sociodemographic characteristics, age was shown to be associated with poorer general health, that is, older judges tend to have a more negative perception of their own health. As expected, increasing age has been shown to be usually associated with a decrease in quality of life and overall health (Pereira et al., 2015). It has also been shown to be associated with higher levels of burnout and, in particular, increased disengagement from work. This means that advancing age seems to be associated with a change in the way judges become detached from the object and the content of their work (Schuster & Dias, 2018). Despite existing contradictory data, age is a major factor in the development of burnout, according to Marchand et al. (2018). While some studies point to a greater age-dependent susceptibility to burnout, with a higher prevalence at older ages (Lindblom et al., 2006), other studies report that some professional areas (e.g., medicine) are characterised by a higher prevalence of burnout at younger ages, suggesting that an explanatory factor could be the existence of a greater set of demands at the beginning of the career (Silveira et al., 2016). The findings of this study do not support the evidence of other studies that show that advancing age translates into a greater ability to manage adverse situations and, consequently, to the development of skills that allow judges to better adapt to the work context, which in turn enables them to manage resources and strategies to combat the factors that trigger the onset of burnout (Alves et al., 2012).

In this research, the gender variable did not appear to be associated with health indicators or burnout, although higher levels of disengagement could be found in male judges. This finding suggests that male judges show greater disengagement, translated into negative behaviours and attitudes towards their work (Sinval et al., 2019). However, several studies have reported a higher prevalence of burnout in women (e.g. Becker et al., 2005; Norlund et al., 2010). According to previous evidence, women are more likely to be the main care providers in the family (Marchand et al., 2018) and work-family reconciliation is often more demanding for women than for men, besides being necessarily more stressful and generating burnout symptoms. Other studies indicate that the incidence of burnout in women can be explained by the accumulation of professional and household duties (Perista et al., 2016).

As regards work characteristics, our findings showed that there is an association between years as judge and the perception of general health: the greater the number of years as judge, the worse the judges' perception of their health. This finding is to some extent associated with the increase in age itself.

The fact that judges are displaced from their usual residence is associated with sleep problems, according to the obtained results. Sleep problems can be a major contributor to decreased wellbeing in workers, with a long-term impact on their safety and health (Magnavita & Garbarino, 2017). A study conducted in South Korea with a working population found that the longer the time and distance between the workplace and the place of residence, the higher the probability of workers developing sleep problems (Kim et al., 2019). Several studies report that certain characteristics of the work context, such as shift work and workload, can result in sleep problems and consequently, sleep disorders in professions related to such sectors as administration, management, agriculture and industry (Gungordu et al., 2023; Young et al., 2017).

One of the major findings was showing that satisfaction with the place of assignment is a determining variable in sleep problems, stress, disengagement, exhaustion and burnout. In other words, the lower the level of satisfaction with the place of assignment, the worse their results in health indicators and burnout levels. It should be noted that

satisfaction with the place of assignment was the only variable that showed an association with stress. This general indicator of judges dis/satisfaction with their place of assignment seems to be a decisive factor in the relationship with health and burnout, showing that the context in which work takes place has the potential to cause psychological, social and physical damage (Ganster & Rosen, 2013; Niedhammer et al., 2021).

The findings obtained from an analysis of the linear regression model tested lead to some considerations that need to be looked at. The predictive model showed that 10.4% of the variance in burnout is explained by the two variables years as judge and satisfaction with the place of assignment. The fact that a greater number of years as judge predicts a higher risk of burnout is a particularly relevant finding if one considers the ageing of the working population in the world of work (Cox et al., 2000; EU-OSHA, 2012). With regard to the effect of satisfaction with the place of assignment, and considering that greater dissatisfaction with one's place of assignment points to a higher risk of developing burnout, a reflection on the assignment of judges in their workplaces is called for. In Portugal, national recruitment procedures in areas such as the judiciary, and also in education, are not always the most satisfactory strategy for the professionals who participate. The way in which the judiciary is assigned their workplaces is a particularly challenging factor and entails, for example, difficulties and demands in terms of balancing professional and family/personal life.

Roach Anleu and Mack's study (2014) on satisfaction in the judicial professions (including judges) reports key findings for analysing this parameter. It shows that family is a factor that can have a major impact on the professional lives of judges, with some gender-related differences. Some findings show that greater dissatisfaction with work, when the new position brings increased duties and fails to provide an adequate number of resources to meet these demands, also increases the risk of burnout (Roach Anleu & Mack, 2014). In addition, the specific characteristics of the jurisdictional area, i.e. factors intrinsic to the legal area in which they work, are also pointed out as factors that generate dissatisfaction, although they were not analysed in this study (Roach Anleu & Mack, 2014).

In sum, dis/satisfaction with the place of assignment is one of the relevant characteristics of judicial work and may be a risk factor or a protective factor in view of the well-known demands to which judges are exposed and which may trigger burnout, decreased mental and physical health, poor overall performance and low job satisfaction (Casaleiro et al., 2021; Chamberlain & Miller, 2009).

8. Conclusions

The increasing interest and concern for the health and general well-being of workers and the changes that have occurred in societies have also created potentially challenging contexts for courts, bringing the attention of researchers to judges as a profession that can and needs to be studied. Accordingly, a project called "Study on working conditions, professional exhaustion, health and well-being of Portuguese judges) was carried out by the Permanent Observatory for Justice of the Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra. From an analysis of the results of the questionnaire applied, from which a sample of 413 respondents was selected, the results for judges sitting in courts of first instance were analysed, focusing on sociodemographic characteristics (age and sex) and work characteristics (years as judge, displacement from the place of residence and satisfaction with the place of assignment) as psychosocial factors that can be potential risk triggers for burnout.

The analysis of these results allows us to respond to our initial objective and draw a set of conclusions. With regard to the association between sociodemographic variables (age, gender) and work variables (years as judge, satisfaction with place of assignment, working away from home), health indicators (stress, sleep problems, overall health) – the findings show that the variable relating to satisfaction with the place of assignment, followed by the variables relating to years as judge and age, are associated with the (lack of) health quality in these professionals, making it more and more precarious as dissatisfaction, number of years as judge and age increase. It thus became clear that dissatisfaction with their place of assignment is the variable with the strongest impact on judges' lives. This dissatisfaction with the place of assignment brings us back to issues concerning judicial professionals' movements, which is the procedure for assigning these professionals in the various courts.

Judicial movements, namely those relating to the assignment of judges in judicial courts of first instance, presuppose certain criteria for their assignment to the different courts in the Portuguese territory. According to the Statute of Judges, decisions concerning the assignment judges should be based on the needs of the service and with minimal detriment to family/personal life. However, compliance with these requirements is not always achieved, especially as regards the consequences of this assignment for each judge. The need to be assigned to a court requires considerable adjustment on the part of these professionals, forcing judges to apply some flexibility in managing their routines. The current situation in Portugal illustrates the impact that working away from home can have on professionals, and there clearly are high levels of dissatisfaction with places of assignment. It is therefore important to understand what impact this dissatisfaction can have on their professional performance and the risk of developing burnout.

With regard to the association between sociodemographic variables (age, gender) and work variables (years as judge, satisfaction with the place of assignment, working away from home) and burnout (disengagement, exhaustion and burnout), as was found in the previous results, the variable relating to satisfaction with the place of assignment, as well as the variables relating to years as judge and age, are also associated with a higher risk of developing burnout. The global analysis of the results obtained, based on a linear regression analysis, does point to a higher risk of burnout related to dissatisfaction with the place of assignment.

These findings suggest that the insecurity and unpredictability inherent in court assignment processes can be a stress factor for the family/personal and professional lives of judges, with potential negative impacts on their health. However, given the important position of judges within society, this impact is not only personal, but can also affect the functioning of justice, reducing productivity and interfering with the quality of judicial decisions, with a natural impact on the justice dispensed to citizens. It can therefore be concluded that these circumstances require that special attention be paid to the way the justice system is organised and managed in Portugal, so that the worrying trends identified in the work context of these professionals can be counteracted.

Following on from the findings obtained, mechanisms should be put in place to prevent and monitor the issues related to the working conditions of these professionals, so that their specific needs can be addressed and the risk of burnout in the profession is reduced. Only then will it be possible to ensure that judges' duties are fulfilled to provide quality work for the benefit of those who seek the courts as a means of guaranteeing effective and efficient justice.

9. References

- Abreu, I., Baía, C., Silva, J., Borges, R., & Pinto, S. (2021). Projeto de Intervenção Burn-Down: o impacto do Burnout nos Cuidados de Saúde Primários e o benefício da Prevenção Quinquenária numa Unidade de Saúde Familiar. *Revista Portuguesa de Saúde Ocupacional Online*, 12, 1-19.
- All European Academies (2018). Código Europeu de Conduta para a Integridade da Investigação. <https://allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/European-Code-of-Conduct-Revised-Edition-2023.pdf>
- Alves, J. C., Ribeiro, C., & Campos, S. (2012). A inteligência emocional em enfermeiros responsáveis por serviços hospitalares. *Referência-Revista de Enfermagem*, 3(7), 33-42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12707/RIII1199>
- Bakker, A. B., Killmer, C. H., Siegrist, J., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2000). Effort-reward imbalance and burnout among nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 31(4), 884-891. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2000.01361.x>
- Becker, J. H., Halbesleben, J. B., & O'Hair, H. D. (2005). Defensive Communication and Burnout in the Workplace: The Mediating Role of Leader-Member Exchange. *Communication Research Reports*, 22(2), 143-150. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00036810500130653>
- Blackham, A. (2019). Reconceiving Judicial Office Through a Labour Law Lens. *Federal Law Review*, 47(2), 203-230. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0067205X19831826>
- Brody, D. C. (2008). The use of judicial performance evaluation to enhance judicial accountability, judicial independence and public trust. *The Denver Law Review*, 86(1), 1-42.
- Campos, J. B., Carlotto, M. S., & Marôco, J. (2012). Oldenburg Burnout Inventory - Student Version: Cultural Adaptation and Validation into Portuguese. *Psicologia: Reflexão e Crítica*, 25(4), 709-718. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0102-79722012000400010>
- Casaleiro, P., Lima, T. M., Relvas, A. P., & Henriques, M. (2021). Condições de trabalho e qualidade de trabalho: reflexões para um estudo das profissões judiciais. *International Journal on Working Conditions*, 18, 83-97. <https://doi.org/10.25762/f60n-1y81>
- Chamberlain, J., & Miller, M. K. (2009). Evidence of Secondary Traumatic Stress, Safety Concerns, and Burnout Among a Homogeneous Group of Judges in a Single Jurisdiction. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law*, 37(2), 214-224.
- Ciociu, M. S., Cojocar, M., & Ciociu, S. V. (2010). Stress related manifestations regarding magistrates. *Romanian Biotechnological Letters*, 15(3), 134-141.
- Collins, J. J., Baase, C. M., Sharda, C. E., Ozminkowski, R. J., Nicholson, S., Billotti, G. M., Turpin, R. S., Olson, M., & Berger, M. L. (2005). The Assessment of Chronic Health Conditions on Work Performance, Absence, and Total Economic Impact for Employers. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 47(6), 547-557. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.jom.0000166864.58664.29>
- Copanitsanou, P., Fotos, N., & Brokalaki, H. (2017). Effects of work environment on patient and nurse outcomes. *British Journal of Nursing*, 26(3), 172-176. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2017.26.3.172>
- Delbrouck, M. (2006). Resumo do Perfil do Candidato à Exaustão. In *Síndrome de Exaustão (burnout) (1st ed., pp. 41-45). Climepsi*.
- Demerouti, E., & Nachreiner, F. (1998). Zur Spezifität von Burnout für Dienstleistungsberufe: Fakt oder Artefakt [The specificity of burnout for human services: Fact or artefact]. *Zeitschrift für Arbeitswissenschaft*, 52, 82-89.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499-512. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.499>

- Dias, J. P., Casaleiro, P., Gomes, C., Jesus, F., Lima, T. M., Queirós, F., & Relvas, A. P. (2024). "Looking at the other side: working conditions in Portuguese courts". *International Journal of Law in Context*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1744552324000028>
- Direção Geral de Saúde. (2021). *Guia Técnico: Vigilância da Saúde dos Trabalhadores Expostos a Fatores de Risco Psicossocial no Local de Trabalho* (3). <https://bussola.gov.pt/Guias%20Prticos/Guia%20t%C3%A9cnico%20vigil%C3%A2ncia%20da%20sa%C3%BAde%20mental%20dos%20trabalhadores%20-%20Vers%C3%A3o%20s%C3%ADntese.pdf>
- Eisch, E., Kuper, P., Lindert, L., & Choi, K. E. (2022). Working Conditions of Occupational Physicians—A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(10), 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19106222>
- EU-OHSA - European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (2009). *OSH in figures: stress at work – facts and figures*. Comunidades Europeias, Luxemburgo. <https://osha.europa.eu/en/publications/osh-figures-stress-work-facts-and-figures>
- EU-OHSA (2012). Mental health promotion in the workplace - a summary of a good practice report. *Factsheet* (102). <https://osha.europa.eu/en/publications/factsheet-102-mental-health-promotion-workplace-summary-good-practice-report>
- Faria, J., Veiga, P., & Ribeiro, J. (2020). Riscos Psicossociais, Saúde e Bem-estar: análise de uma empresa de Cablagem em Portugal. *Revista Portuguesa de Saúde Ocupacional Online*, 9, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.31252/RPSO.30.05.2020>
- Flores, D. M., Miller, M. K., Chamberlain, J., Richardson, J. T., & Bornstein, B. H. (2009). Judges Perspectives on Stress and Safety in the Courtroom: An exploratory Study. *Court Review*, 45, 76-89. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.998303>
- Ganster, D. C., & Rosen, C. C. (2013). Work Stress and Employee Health A Multidisciplinary Review. *Journal of Management*, 39(5), 1085-1122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206313475815>
- Gomes, R. (2022). Stress, cognitive appraisal, and burnout in social workers of residential child care. *Revista de Psicologia*, 40(2), 1075-1097. <https://doi.org/10.18800/psico.202202.016>
- Guimarães, T. A., Filho, E. G., & Luz, B. C. (2020). Courts as Organizations: Governance and Legitimacy. *Brazilian Administration Review*, 17(4), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-7692bar2020200032>
- Gungordu, N., Kurtul, S., & Erdogan, M. S. (2023). Evaluation of Sleep Quality, Work Stress and Related Factors in Hospital Office Workers. *La Medicina del Lavoro*, 114(3), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.23749/mdl.v114i3.14033>
- Gupta, N. D., & Kristensen, N. (2008). Work environment satisfaction and employee health: panel evidence from Denmark, France and Spain, 1994–2001. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 9, 51-61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10198-007-0037-6>
- Hassell, K. D., Archbold, C. A., & Stichman, A. J. (2010). Comparing the workplace experiences of male and female police officers: examining workplace problems, stress, job satisfaction and consideration of career change. *International Journal of Police Science and Management*, 13(1), 37-53. <https://doi.org/10.1350/ijps.2011.13.1.217>
- International Labour Office (ILO). (1986). *Psychosocial factors at work: Recognition and control. Report of the Joint International Labour Office and World Health Organization on Occupational Health*. Occupational Safety and Health Series (56). International Labour Office. https://ilo.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay/alma992480113402676/41ILO_INST:411LO_V2
- Jain, A., Hassard, J., Leka, S., Di Tecco, C., & Iavicoli, S. (2021). The Role of Occupational Health Services in Psychosocial Risk Management and the Promotion of Mental Health and Well-Being at Work. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(3632). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073632>

- Kim, S., Kim, Y., Lim, S., Ryoo, J., & Yoon, J. (2019). Long Commute Time and Sleep Problems with Gender Difference in Work-Life Balance: A Cross-sectional Study of More than 25,000 Workers. *Safety and Health at Work*, 10(4), 470-475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2019.08.001>
- Kline, R. B. (2011). Data Preparation. In *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling* (3rd ed., pp. 46-74). The Guildford Press.
- Kristensen, T., Hannerz, H., Hogh, A. & Borg, V. (2005). The Copenhagen psychosocial Questionnaire – a tool for the assessment and improvement of the psychosocial work environment. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment and Health*, 31(6), 438-449. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.948>
- Lian, L., Guo, S., Wang, Q., Hu, L., Yang, X., & Li, X. (2021). Calling, character strengths, career identity, and job burnout in young Chinese university teachers: A chain-mediating model. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 120, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105776>
- Lindblom, K. M., Linton, S. J., Fedeli, C., & Bryngelsson, I. (2006). Burnout in the Working Population: Relations to Psychosocial Work Factors. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 13(1), 51-59. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327558ijbm1301_7
- Little, R.J.A. (1988) A Test of Missing Completely at Random for Multivariate Data with Missing Values. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 83, 1198-1202. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1988.10478722>
- Magnavita, N., & Garbarino, S. (2017). Sleep, health and wellness at work: a scoping review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(11), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14111347>
- Malagris, L. N., & Fiorito, A. C. (2006). Avaliação do nível de stress de técnicos da área de saúde. *Estudos de Psicologia*, 23(4), 391-398. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-166X2006000400007>
- Marchand, A., Blanc, M., & Beauregard, N. (2018). Do age and gender contribute to workers' burnout symptoms? *Occupational Medicine*, 68(6), 405-411. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqy088>
- Marchand, A., Demers, A., & Durand, P. (2005). Do occupation and work conditions really matter? A longitudinal analysis of psychological distress experiences among Canadian workers. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 27(5), 602-627. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9566.2005.00458.x>
- Miller, M. K., & Flores, D. M. (2007). Addressing the Problem of Courtroom Stress. *Judicature*, 91(2), 60-69.
- Mota, B. S., Figueiredo, S. N., Siqueira, D. G., Queiroz, N. A., & Santos, T. P. (2020). As contribuições da síndrome de burnout para o déficit do trabalho da enfermagem: revisão integrativa da literatura. *Revista Eletrônica Acervo Saúde*, 12(10), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.25248/reas.e4383.2020>
- Na, C., Choo, T., & Klingfuss, J. A. (2017). The Causes and Consequences of Job-Related Stress among Prosecutors. *The American Journal of Criminal Justice*, 43, 329-353. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12103-017-9396-4>
- Niedhammer, I., Bertrais, S., & Witt, K. (2021). Psychosocial work exposures and health outcomes: a meta-review of 72 literature reviews with meta-analysis. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment and Health*, 47(7), 489-508. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.3968>
- Norlund, S., Reuterwall, C., Hoog, J., & Lindahl, B. (2010). Burnout, working conditions and gender - Results from the northern Sweden MONICA Study. *BMC Public Health*, 10(1), 326. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-10-326>
- Pereira, D. S., Nogueira, J. D., & Silva, c. B. (2015). Qualidade de vida e situação de saúde de idosos: um estudo de base populacional no Sertão Central do Ceará. *Revista Brasileira de Geriatria e Gerontologia*, 18(4), 893-908. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-9823.2015.14123>

- Pereira, S. M., Correia, P. R., Palma, P. J., Pitacho, L., & Lunardi, F. C. (2022). The Conceptual Model of Role Stress and Job Burnout in Judges: The Moderating Role of Career Calling. *Laws*, 11(42), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws11030042>
- Perista, H., Cardoso, A., Brázia, A., Abrantes, M., & Perista, P. (2016). Tempo em família. In Centro de Estudos para a Intervenção Social & Comissão para a Igualdade no Trabalho e no Emprego (Eds.), *Os Usos do Tempo de Homens e de Mulheres em Portugal* (pp. 57-124).
- Queirós, P. P. (2005). Burnout no trabalho e conjugal nos enfermeiros e o clima organizacional. *Revista Investigação em Enfermagem*, 11, 3-15.
- Ribeiro, P., Almada, D., Souto, J., & Lourenço, R. (2018). Permanência no mercado de trabalho e satisfação com a vida na velhice. *Ciência e Saúde Coletiva*, 23(8), 2683-2692. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232018238.20452016>
- Richards, K. R., Hemphill, M. A., & Templin, T. J. (2018). Personal and contextual factors related to teachers' experience with stress and burnout. *Teachers and Teaching*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2018.1476337>
- Roach Anleu, S., & Mack, K. (2014). Job satisfaction in the Judiciary. *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(5), 683-701. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017013500111>
- Rosário, S., Azevedo, L. F., Fonseca, J. A., Nienhaus, A., Nubling, M., & Costa, J. T. (2017). The Portuguese long version of the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire II (COPSOQ II) - a validation study. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, 12(24), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-017-0170-9>
- Sadir, M. A., Bignotto, M. M., & Lipp, M. N. (2010). Stress e qualidade de vida: influência de algumas variáveis pessoais. *Paideia*, 20(45), 73-81. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-863X2010000100010>
- Santana, L. L., Sarquis, L. M., & Miranda, F. M. (2020). Riscos psicossociais e a saúde dos trabalhadores de saúde: reflexões sobre a Reforma Trabalhista Brasileira. *Revista Brasileira de Enfermagem*, 73(0). <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2019-0092>
- Sauter, S. L., Brightwell, W. S., Colligan, M. J., Hurrell Jr., J., Katz, T. M., LeGrande, D. E., Lessin, N., Lippin, R. A., Lipscomb, J. A., Murphy, L. R., Peters, R. H., Keita, G. P., Robertson, S. R., Stellman, J. M., Swanson, N. G., & Tetric, L. E. (2002). *The Changing Organization of Work and the Safety and Health of Working People* (116). National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health.
- Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). Applying the Job Demands-Resources model: A 'how to' guide to measuring and tackling work engagement and burnout. *Organizational Dynamics*, 46(2), 120-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2017.04.008>
- Schuster, M. S., Dias, V. V. (2018). Oldenburg Burnout Inventory – validação de uma nova forma de mensurar Burnout no Brasil. *Ciência e Saúde Coletiva*, 23(2), 553-562. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232018232.27952015>
- Sharma, A., Verma, S., Verma, c., & Malhotra, D. (2010). Stress and Burnout as Predictors of Job Satisfaction amongst Lawyers. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(3), 348-359. http://www.bwgriffin.com/gsu/courses/edur9131/assessments/test1_sharmaejss_14_3_01.pdf
- Silva, C., Amaral, V., Pereira, A., Bem-haja, P., Pereira, A., Rodrigues, V., Cotrim, T., Silvério, J., & Nossa, P. (2012). *Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire - COPSOQ - Portugal e países africanos de língua oficial portuguesa* (1st ed.). C. Fernandes da Silva (Ed.). Universidade de Aveiro.
- Silveira, A. P., Colleta, T. D., Ono, H. B., Woltas, L. R., Soares, S. H., Andrade, V. A., & Araújo, L. A. (2016). Síndrome de Burnout: consequências e implicações de uma realidade cada vez mais prevalente na vida dos profissionais de saúde. *Revista Brasileira de Medicina do Trabalho*, 14(3), 275-284. <https://doi.org/10.5327/Z1679-443520163215>
- Sinval, J., Queirós, C., Pasian, S., & Marôco, J. (2019). Transcultural Adaptation of the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) for Brazil and Portugal. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00338>

- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2001). *Using Multivariate Statistics* (4th ed.). Allyn and Bacon.
- Tsai, F. J., & Chan, C. C. (2010). Occupational stress and burnout of judges and procurators. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 83, 133-142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00420-009-0454-1>
- Tsai, F., Huang, W., & Chan, C. (2009). Occupational Stress and Burnout of Lawyers. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 51(5), 443-450. <https://doi.org/10.1539/joh.L8179>
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2022). *ICD-11 – International Classification of Diseases*. World Health Organization. <https://icd.who.int/en>
- Young, L. C., Li, J., & Calvert, G. M. (2017). Sleep-related problems in the US working population: prevalence and association with shiftwork status. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 74(2), 93-104. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2016-103638>